

Conceptualising Ignorance Logics in Search — with Examples of Environmental Issues

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1. Introduction

Algorithmic information systems, such as corporate web search engines or information access systems with retrieval augmented generation (RAG), filter vast amounts of data to deliver specific outputs and recommendations. In the process, certain data is selected, ordered and presented, while other data and ways of ordering are omitted from an issue's informational texture (Haider, 2016). The notion of "new knowledge logics" (Gillespie, 2014) has been influential in scholarship by drawing attention to the involvement of algorithmic systems in shaping knowledge, as well as what can be known and how. Nevertheless, greater attention should be paid to new regimes of non-knowledge, of being unknowable, and of not knowing, which are equally tied to the infrastructural arrangements supported by these platforms. These regimes and how they emerge and persist necessitate further conceptual refinement. The purpose of this contribution is therefore to conceptualise what we propose to call *ignorance logics*, focusing in particular on their algorithmic configuration. This will provide a conceptual basis for exploring the multiplicity of worlds that are made less likely, less plausible, or even invisible through these algorithmic decisions of online search engines and RAG systems.

2. Background

Ignorance is more than just the opposite of knowledge. Rather, the notion of ignorance describes the many ways in which things are not or cannot be known or engaged with and how they are made unknowable: intentionally and unintentionally, self-enforced, directed by others, an emergent property of an information system, or strategic and so on (Proctor and Schiebinger, 2008; McGoey, 2012; Greyson, 2019). Clearly, high-risk issues are characterised not only by different knowledge regimes and forms of evidence and, but also by ignorances (White & Lidskog, 2022). Therefore, we need to pay attention to the sociomaterial configurations involved in the emergence of the invisibilities, silences and blind spots in the present data economy (Deepak et al., 2024). Examining these configurations will also broaden our understanding of the ways in which high-risk issues concerning the environment and climate, increasingly emerge not from a consolidation but from the disjunction of research-based evidence, public knowledge, policy advice, political discourse, public perception and media perpetuated by internet search engines along with other algorithmic information systems.

Examples of environmental issues that are structured around such forms of ignorance and not knowing include areas as diverse as climate change, biodiversity loss, pollution, or ocean acidification; all issues where research-based evidence points in the same direction, but significant change fails to materialise for a variety of reasons (White & Lidskog, 2023; Stoddard et al., 2021), including the way search engines embed different types of relevance (Haider & Rödl, 2023). Even more than conventional web search engines, RAG renders underlying semantic relationships and relevance decisions invisible

(Haider, 2024), further emphasising the need to pay attention to, examine, and conceptualise ignorance logics.

3. Concept Development

In this contribution, we seek to develop the foundations for a conceptual understanding of ignorance logics by integrating empirical illustrations and discussions of strategically selected examples with theoretical considerations. These examples are presented in the form of screenshots as well as descriptive and analytical explanations. The contribution explores some of the entities, actors and concepts involved (e.g. search algorithms, search engine optimisation, queries and prompts, knowledge graphs, Wikipedia, Reddit, malicious actors, etc.). It furthermore examines the types of relationships they enter, the opportunities for configuring ignorances they afford (from malicious interference to deliberate avoidance), as well as the potential effects or harms on individual and societal engagement with the issues described (from invisibility and data voids to uncertainty and doubt).

The role of search engines at the intersection of ignorance logics and environmental issues includes the more readily noticeable spread of climate denial and obstruction (Rödl & Haider, 2025), but also extends to algorithmic normalisation of extremist or conspiratorial views, the undermining of public acceptance for environmental protection and regulation, the perpetuation of discrimination and oppressive power relations, and not least to the ways in which search engines and RAG embed consumerist values that facilitate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Haider et al., 2022) and climate destruction by design (Haider et al., 2025). For example, employing chain-of-thought prompting to instruct a RAG-based conversational agent to explain a search strategy and associated query formulation (even if justified only in hindsight), helps to reveal biases and normative assumptions that manifest in algorithmically enacted ignorance logics. In the context of environmental concerns, this tactic serves to highlight consumerist biases linked to increased greenhouse gas emissions and to examine how manipulation occurs through data voids (see examples in the screenshots in the Appendix, Figures 1-4).

Although the selected examples in this contribution are all derived from content and topics related to environmental concerns, the concept's usefulness extends beyond this specific domain. The conceptual and analytical emphasis on ignorance logics draws attention to the ways in which search engines, alongside other algorithmic information systems, are involved in creating silences, reinforcing ignorances, and rendering certain relationships and associations invisible. Compared to traditional search engine results, RAG adds a further layer that needs to be peeled off in order to understand what results are even retrieved, how many there are, and how they are ordered. The outsourcing and obfuscation of source selection and of iterative query formulation (i.e. searching) creates opportunities for new, potentially exploitable, ignorances. At the same time, as the examples in this paper illustrate, this additional layer can also act as a methodological lens that makes ignorance logics more noticeable, and thereby contestable.

4. Conclusion

Traditional, link-based, web search engines and the newly emerging AI-infused retrieval systems (RAG), that are euphemistically advertised as answer machines, contribute not only to making things known, but also to obscuring them, to situating sustainable practices outside cultural norms, and to creating doubt about legitimate environmental concerns. As part of collective meaning-making on environmental issues and the climate crisis, ignorance logics have real implications for knowledge and action in everyday life, society and politics, and for the possibilities for meaningful environmental change. Studying, conceptualizing, and thinking with these logics also provides an opening for

renegotiating values and norms and for challenging the infrastructural arrangements that maintain them. Doing so will help formulate new, unfamiliar, and presumably even uncomfortable questions about the role of search engines in society, such as: What ignorances could there be? How would they be configured? What interests are and what interests could be served? As such, paying attention to ignorance logics, is both a conceptual contribution, a methodological tactic, and a powerful invitation to challenge the emancipatory promises of information systems.

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7. Screenshots exemplifying ignorance logics

The screenshot shows a Copilot chat interface. At the top right, a blue button contains the text "What is 'Climate Intelligence'?". Below this, the Copilot logo is followed by the heading "Copilot". The main text of the response describes Climate Intelligence (Clintel) as an independent foundation established in 2019 by emeritus professor of geophysics Guus Berkhout and science journalist Marcel Crok. It lists five main objectives: 1. Generating Knowledge, 2. Communication, 3. Public Debate, 4. Scientific Research, and 5. International Collaboration. Below the list, it mentions the World Climate Declaration and provides links to the organization's official website. At the bottom, there are two search suggestions: "What are Clintel's main criticisms of IPCC?" and "How many scientists support the World Climate Declaration?". The interface also shows a "Message Copilot" input field with a paperclip icon and a send button.

What is "Climate Intelligence"?

Copilot

Climate Intelligence (Clintel) is an independent foundation established in 2019 by emeritus professor of geophysics Guus Berkhout and science journalist Marcel Crok ¹ ². The organization aims to inform the public about climate change and climate policies. Clintel's main objectives include:

1. **Generating Knowledge:** Understanding the causes and effects of climate change and the impact of climate policies on the economy and environment.
2. **Communication:** Objectively and transparently communicating available facts about climate change and climate policy, distinguishing between facts, assumptions, and predictions.
3. **Public Debate:** Stimulating public debate and conducting investigative reporting on climate-related issues.
4. **Scientific Research:** Conducting or financing scientific research into climate change and climate policy.
5. **International Collaboration:** Serving as a meeting place for scientists with diverse views on climate change and policy ².

Clintel is known for its World Climate Declaration, which asserts that there is no climate emergency. This declaration has been signed by numerous scientists and experts worldwide ¹ ².

For more detailed information, you can visit their [official website](#).

¹: [Clintel - Climate Intelligence](#) ²: [Clintel - About Us](#)

¹ Climate Intelligence (CLIN... ² About us - Clintel

What are Clintel's main criticisms of IPCC? How many scientists support the World Climate Declaration?

Message Copilot

@ | ▶

Figure 1: Screenshot of Copilot response page for the search prompt "What is 'Climate Intelligence'?"

Explain the search carried out. What queries did you use and why did you choose those?

When researching children's clothing options in Sweden, particularly around Borås, I focused on identifying reputable brands and retailers that cater to various needs, including sustainability, affordability, and style. Here's an overview of the search queries and the rationale behind each:

🔍 Search Queries and Their Purpose

1. "children's clothing brands Sweden sustainable kidswear"

- **Purpose:** To find Swedish brands that prioritize sustainability and offer eco-friendly children's clothing.
- **Findings:** This led to brands like [Moromini](#), known for their colorful, GOTS-certified organic clothes, and [Oersaa](#), a micro-brand focusing on sustainable products with hand-painted prints.

[moromini - organic kids clothes](#)

2. "popular Swedish children's clothing brands"

- **Purpose:** To identify well-known Swedish brands that offer a range of children's clothing.
- **Findings:** Discovered brands such as [Polarn O. Pyret](#), recognized for durable and stylish children's clothing, and [Mini Rodini](#), celebrated for imaginative designs and commitment to sustainability.

3. "online retailers children's clothing Sweden"

- **Purpose:** To find online platforms where one can purchase children's clothing in Sweden.
- **Findings:** Identified retailers like [Lindex](#), a market leader in kids' wear in Sweden, and [Kids Brand Store](#), Nordic's largest online store for children's and youth fashion. [lindex.info](#)

🛍️ Product Recommendations

Based on the research, here are some product recommendations that align with sustainable practices and are available in Sweden:

Fråga vad som helst

+ Sök Resonera Djup research Skapa bild ...

ChatGPT kan begå misstag. Kontrollera viktig information.

Figure 2: Screenshot of a SearchGPT response page showing an explanation for the search prompt "children's clothes".

Figure 3: Screenshot of a You.com response page for the search prompt "Copenhagen Vienna"

Figure 4: Screenshot of a You.com response page showing an explanation the response to the search prompt "Copenhagen Vienna"